

Nested-Sigma Conjecture

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Abstract. In this paper, we provide the Nested-Sigma Conjecture.

Conjecture. *Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $k \in \mathbb{N}$, and let $a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_k$ be index of summation. Then,*

$$\sum_{a_1=1}^n \sum_{a_2=1}^{a_1} \sum_{a_3=1}^{a_2} \cdots \sum_{a_k=1}^{a_{k-1}} a_k = \frac{n(n+1)(n+2) \cdots (n+k)}{(k+1)!} = \prod_{i=0}^k \frac{n+i}{1+i} \quad (1)$$

Example 1. Show that **Conjecture** is true at $k = 1$.

$$\sum_{k=1}^n k = \frac{n(n+1)}{2} = \frac{n(n+1)}{2!} \quad (2)$$

Example 2. Show that **Conjecture** is true at $k = 2$.

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^i k = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{i(i+1)}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n i^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n i \right) \quad (3)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{n(n+1)(2n+1)}{6} + \frac{n(n+1)}{2} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$= \frac{n(n+1)(n+2)}{3!} \quad (5)$$

Example 3. Show that **Conjecture** is true at $k = 3$.

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^i \sum_{k=1}^j k = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\sum_{j=1}^i \sum_{k=1}^j k \right) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{i(i+1)(i+2)}{3!} \quad (6)$$

$$= \frac{1}{6} \sum_{i=1}^n i^3 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n i^2 + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^n i \quad (7)$$

$$= \frac{1}{6} \cdot \frac{n^2(n+1)^2}{4} + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{n(n+1)(2n+1)}{6} + \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{n(n+1)}{2} \quad (8)$$

$$= \frac{n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)}{4!} \quad (9)$$